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EFFECTIVE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TRANSITION TO A DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: In this article the use of modern information technologies in education, the development of effective approaches, the introduction of advanced teaching methods to familiarise the younger generation with the achievements of world civilisation, the radical improvement of the system of training potential specialists, the use of the world's information resources aimed at ensuring their wide use and the effective use of their technologies.

Electronic commerce is the sale of goods (works, services) within the framework of business activities using information systems in accordance with the contract concluded through an electronic trading platform. In order to liberalize the economy and reduce administrative regulation in our country, to increase market mechanisms in the sale of highly liquid and monopolistic products, and to increase the level of transparency in stock exchange trading and to develop a healthy competitive environment, it is necessary to introduce modern information and communication technologies into the stock market. consistent measures are being taken.

Keywords: information technology, Macro Media Flash, GIF animation, Microsoft Front Page.

INTRODUCTION

We see that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has paid attention to youth and named the year 2021 "Supporting youth and promoting health".

The education system in our country promotes the widespread use of information and communications technology in teaching school subjects. Information technology is a universal tool for education. Modern technologies not only shape students' knowledge, skills and abilities, but also play an important role in guiding them to learn, develop their personal qualities and increase their interest in learning. ICTs have a major impact in broadening students' horizons, horizons, creativity, theoretical knowledge and reflective thinking. In essence, ICT broadens students' imaginative thinking and helps them to assimilate scientific knowledge more easily and intimately.

Since the first days of independence, special attention has been paid to education in order to educate the younger generation, who are the masters of our future.

The future, prosperity and development of our independent country depends largely on the upbringing of the younger generation. This requires creating favourable conditions for the future of our country - for the physical, mental and spiritual development of our children.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY (LITERATURE REVIEW)

N.O.Yoldoshev and M.P.Yunusov suggest using the following approaches to the concept of the stock market in the analysis of commodity exchange trade [1] Commodity exchanges embody market mechanisms such as competition, demand, supply, price, and price. The exchange is a place where, on the one hand, the seller, who wants to sell goods, and, on the other hand, the buyer, who is trying to satisfy his demand, meet, both of them are independent economic entities. The buying and selling process is carried out through intermediaries - brokers, dealers, traders. In

the stock market, as in other markets, the price of goods is directly related to supply and demand. If the manufacturer brings a new, improved product to the market, he has the right to pay a higher price for his product [2,3].

Development of goods production in agriculture determines the objective need to form a market with appropriate categories and regulatory methods. In practice, there are two types of relations between the producer and the consumer. The first is carried out in accordance with the laws of production and circulation of goods using the market as an exchange. The second is the distribution of the produced product based on the requirements of study and accounting balance [4,5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Digitization of the economy requires the teaching of economic knowledge through information and communication technologies. The main goal of introducing the teaching of economic knowledge through information and communication technologies is to create a modern education system [6].

A modern teacher is required to be able to use information technology in the classroom, to teach students to assimilate modern knowledge thoroughly, to become mature individuals, and to use computers freely.

The experience of using ICT creates unlimited possibilities for individualization and differentiation of the learning processes in the case of didactically correct use of ICT in traditional lessons. They make it possible to introduce new forms and methods of teaching.

During the lesson, various presentations and projects were created using off-the-shelf multimedia programmes and computer learning tools [7, 8]. The use of information technology is possible in all subjects. The full-fledged passage of lessons is influenced by the conduct of the educational process using new interactive methods and information technology, for example, the use of multimedia in the course of the lesson and the use of the Internet (1- Figure).

Figure 1: The role of modern ICT in education.

By using modern computer technology, teachers can address the following tasks:

- this method of teaching activates students' thinking abilities and increases the efficiency of material learning;
- enables them to simulate and visualise processes which are difficult or complicated to demonstrate;

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- learning material is effective not only in terms of level, but also in terms of students' logic and acceptance;
- Students are given the opportunity to search for and find material and to find answers to problematic questions through independent research;
- conditions are created for students to quickly master the new topic, solve examples, write essays, reports, familiarise themselves with learning materials, select and analyse information and data [9, 10].

Modern education requires teachers to use advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in the learning process (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Modern technology in education.

Every teacher should be creative and inquisitive. Every lesson needs to be new and thoroughly prepared. Students become bored with monotony and their attitudes to the lesson weaken. The result is less effective lessons. The role of lessons with the use of information technology in the activity of a teacher is expressed in the following: - Correct distribution of time; - Provision of bright and convincing content of educational material; - Increase in the volume of information provided; - Expansion of types of learning tasks; - Creation of healthy competition, creative environment; - Regular improvement of professional qualification.

Today in Uzbekistan, a special market for programmes used as a didactic tool in the educational process is being formed. There are many programmes available on the Internet that can be used in general education classes. These include, first and foremost, electronic textbooks, and their technology makes it possible to use various interactive tasks. For example, students can arrange events in chronological order, correctly explain terms and concepts related to science, or indicate terms in the right and left rows and their meaning with an arrow, or write key words in a given topic, they will be able to learn how they performed tasks such as completing test assignments and crossword puzzles by comparing them with the answers displayed on a large screen using multimedia.

CONCLUSION.

The use of modern information and communication technologies in lessons helps students to think independently, to search creatively, to increase their interest in the lesson, to connect what they learn in the lesson with life, to expand their logical observations and thus to become modern and mature professionals. It guarantees quality education and learning based on advanced, innovative, pedagogical and communicative technologies by teachers using modern technology.

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